

EXPERIENCE IN ORGANIZING MENTORSHIP AND THE “MASTER-APPRENTICE” SYSTEM IN FOREIGN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Abdullaeva Sabohat Gayratullaevna,
Doctoral student at Navoi State University
Lecturer at the Navoi branch of Profi University

Annotation: This article analyzes the pedagogical experience of organizing mentorship and the “mentor-apprentice” system in foreign higher education institutions. The content, forms, and educational significance of mentoring mechanisms used in universities in the USA, Great Britain, Japan, and South Korea are highlighted. It also reveals the specific aspects of developing cooperation between students and educators based on values.

During the study, the positive impact of the mentorship system on students' professional competence, spiritual and moral development, and social adaptation was analyzed based on scientific sources.

Keywords: mentoring, teacher-student, axiological approach, higher education, pedagogical cooperation, foreign experience, values, academic mentorship.

Introduction

In today's globalization process, one of the important pedagogical tasks in the higher education system is considered not only to impart knowledge but also to support the spiritual, professional, and social development of the student. Therefore, in many foreign universities, special attention is paid to the “mentorship” and “mentor-student” systems. This system serves to strengthen interaction between the teacher and the student, support individual development, and ensure the exchange of professional experience.

In particular, mentoring relationships organized on the basis of an axiological approach are an important factor in the formation of students' respect for national and universal values, responsibility, professional ethics, and social activity. In this regard, studying the experience of foreign higher education institutions and adapting it to the national education system is one of the urgent issues.

Pedagogical essence of the mentoring system in foreign universities. In foreign pedagogical practice, mentorship is interpreted as the process of an experienced specialist assisting a young student or young educator in their professional and personal development. A mentor acts not only as an educator but also as a guiding, motivating, and psychological support person.

Today, the mentoring system in universities of developed countries is implemented in the following areas:

- academic mentorship;
- scientific leadership;
- psychological support;
- professional development;
- social adaptation;
- peer mentoring.

These systems play an important role in the student's rapid adaptation to the university environment, the formation of independent learning skills, and preparation for professional activity.

Mentorship system in US universities. In the US higher education system, mentorship is one of the primary mechanisms ensuring the individual development of a student. At universities

such as Harvard, Stanford, and the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), an academic mentor is assigned to each student.

The main tasks of mentors are:

- determining the student's educational trajectory;
- orientation toward scientific research;
- providing recommendations on professional activities;
- psychological support;
- developing leadership skills.

The “peer mentoring” system is also widespread in US universities, where senior students help new students adapt to the university environment. This system develops a sense of cooperation, social activity, and responsibility among students.

Furthermore, an individual approach to the student is of paramount importance in mentoring activities. This is based on the student's interests, abilities, and needs.

The experience of the “tutorial system” in UK universities. The “tutorial system” model has been in effect since ancient times at the universities of Oxford and Cambridge in Great Britain. This system is based on individual communication between the student and the professor.

During the tutorial sessions:

- students present their independent scientific works;
- conducts discussions with the professor;
- develops critical thinking skills;
- learns to reason scientifically.

The main advantage of this system is that the student is in constant scientific and spiritual contact with the teacher. As a result, mutual respect, academic culture, and intellectual cooperation are formed.

In UK universities, mentorship is viewed not only as a means of imparting knowledge but also as a means of educating the individual. This is a practical expression of the axiological approach.

The "Senpai-Kohai" system in Japanese universities. The “Senpai-Kohai” tradition holds a special place in the Japanese education system. “Senpai” means experienced senior, and “Kohai” means young or inexperienced person.

In this system:

- senior students support younger students;
- professors act as educational leaders;
- the values of respect, discipline, and responsibility are priorities.

In Japan, mentoring relationships are more based on spiritual and moral values. The student learns to treat the teacher with respect, work in a team, and take social responsibility.

One of the important aspects of this system is that mutual trust and loyalty are considered the fundamental principles of pedagogical relations.

Mentorship experience at South Korean universities. The mentoring system in South Korean universities will be organized in integration with digital technologies. Online mentoring platforms operate in many universities.

Through this system:

- the student's academic activity is monitored;
- an individual development map is maintained;
- regular communication is established between the mentor and the student;
- professional planning is carried out.

In the Korean experience, the primary goal of mentorship is to train a competitive, spiritually mature, and innovative-thinking specialist.

Pedagogical conclusions based on foreign experience. Analysis shows that the mentorship and “master-apprentice” system in foreign universities is based on the following pedagogical principles:

- individual approach;
- cooperation pedagogy;
- value-oriented education;
- reflective activity;
- continuous development;
- psychological support.

These experiences demonstrate the need to develop “master-apprentice” traditions within the higher education system of Uzbekistan based on modern pedagogical technologies.

Conclusion

The experience of foreign higher education institutions shows that mentorship and the “master-apprentice” system are important pedagogical mechanisms for the professional and spiritual development of a student. Mentorship models used in universities in the USA, Great Britain, Japan, and South Korea serve to form effective cooperation between students and educators.

The mentorship system, organized on the basis of an axiological approach, serves as an effective tool for developing the spiritual values of youth, strengthening their professional competencies, and increasing their social activity. Therefore, it is important to develop a modern “master-apprentice” model in higher education by adapting foreign experience to the national education system.

References

1. Comparative pedagogy. Study guide. A.A. Ikramov, G.N. Davronova, A.A. Ikramova. 2023
2. Comparative pedagogy. Educational and methodological complex. R. Tukhtasheva. Samarkand 2021.
3. Comparavite Adult Education and learning Authors and Texts edited by Maria Slowey. firenze university press 2016
<https://books.fupress.com/catalogue/comparative-adult-education-and-learning/3363>
https://hollis.harvard.edu/primo-explore/search?vid=HVD2&sortby=rank&lang=eng_US
4. Pedagogy of Freedom — New York: Rowman & Littlefield, 1998.
5. The Essential Guide to Mentoring — London, 2004.
6. Materials from Harvard University's official mentoring programs.